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PEDAGOGY OF ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN COURSES AND CASE STUDIES IN STUDIOS OF NBTE-ACCREDITED POLYTECHNICS, SOUTHEAST NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper discusses teaching and learning in the design studio in Architectural Education in NBTE-accredited polytechnics in Southeast Nigeria. Architectural design courses are subset of professional courses which give the students theory and practical skills needed to practice the profession at the technician/technologist level as specified by the National Board for Technical Education Curriculum and Course Specifications for ND/HND Architectural Technology. These may account for 70-80% of the total contact hours. A case study of the Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri and Abia State Polytechnic, Aba, Abia State is presented. The study maintains that the design studio is central to architectural programme and the practice of architecture. It emphasizes the need for an improvement in the architecture curriculum particularly in the assessment of case studies which will go a long way in improving the overall performance of students in jury sessions.

Keywords: case study, contact hours, curriculum, design studio, jury.

INTRODUCTION

The definition of pedagogy includes the theory and practice of teaching, the strategies employed in order to teach, the specific interaction of teacher and students, the instructive content used, the combined goals of the learner and teacher and the way the content is presented and delivered to the learner.

Pedagogy in education describes the carefully thought-out process a teacher will use to teach their students, taking into account prior learning, classroom context, end goals and more. Pedagogy is often described on a spectrum with teacher-centered pedagogy on the one end, and learner-centered pedagogy on the other. Effective teaching involves using the ideal pedagogy at different times, in different contexts to support the very best learning outcomes (Barton, 2019).

Teacher-centered pedagogy, as the name implies, places the teacher front and center as the impartor of information, while the students are the recipients of the knowledge. This can take the form of a class lecture or 'parrot-fashion' rote learning or following in a text book. This is the most traditional teaching method and is often criticized in educational discussions. However, it certainly has its place, and is best used for specific, factual learning or the introduction of a brand-new concept. It is most effective when the teacher and students have a good relationship, and the students are comfortable speaking and asking questions. **Learner-centered pedagogy** grants the learners a more active role in the process of learning, excellent for incorporating and building on prior knowledge taught. By accessing prior knowledge and bringing in new experiences, the next level of learning is created. *This pedagogical strategy sees the teacher as a facilitator to the process, a part of the process more than the main focus of*

it. Many educators believe this is very effective in stimulating individual cognition and a more experiential learning environment, which usually means greater understanding and retention.

All teachers would like their classroom management style to be considered a dynamic learning environment, characterized by change, activity and progress. An inclusive classroom benefits every child in it. Not everyone learns at the same pace, and has the same aptitude. By carefully including learners who might have learning, attention or behavioral issues, stigma is reduced, and a happier environment is maintained. Technology in the classroom is here to stay, and the educator who does not incorporate it will be doing their students a great disservice. Combining the use of technology with both modern and traditional teaching methods (blended learning) is imperative. Service Learning utilizes technology as a tool to help learning throughout the five stages- Investigation, Planning/Preparation, Action and Demonstration/Communication. Service learning entails the creative integration of academic concepts and content in specific subjects and practical application of 'Action' in the real world, in order to consolidate the academic theory and meet a need that is identified with the community. On top of the obvious learning benefits, the community, the learners and educators are all enriched through the experience.

Service learning can only be possible through good teaching which requires a fine blend of subject knowledge, teaching methodology, psychology of learning and of learners, and an especially relevant creative attitudinal orientation on the part of the teacher. The outcome of such 'good teaching' - trenchant teaching, ultimately leads to effective learning. It means thorough and lasting acquisition of the knowledge, skills and values the teacher or the institution has set out to impart (Olotuah, Taiwo, & Ijatuyi, 2016).

The design studio is the work space and the primary course of study of architecture students in NBTE accredited Schools of Architecture. The greater part of the architecture programme centers on the design studio and it thus has a pre-eminent position. It is the hub of the architectural programme. The acquisition of skills by architecture students is made possible in the design studio. As it is the major concern of the architecture programme the design studio is often assigned about 50% (fifty percent) of course units required for graduation. The entire architectural programme thus culminates in the design studio where students develop the skills for effectively shaping, ordering and articulating the built environment. Learning in the design studio is therefore of crucial importance in the study of Architecture and it is contingent upon the teaching methodology and curriculum of the school. Of the five NBTE accredited Schools of Architecture in Southeast Nigeria subjective sampling was adopted in the selection of Abia State Polytechnic, Aba, Abia State and Federal Polytechnic, Nekede, Owerri, Imo State for study. The curricula of these institutions were examined in this paper to show their coverage, direction and emphasis. The pedagogical methods of teaching, learning and evaluation in the design studio of all schools were discussed. The paper further discusses the contents of the course curricula with regard to assessment modules which is geared towards objective and participatory evaluation of independent case studies prepared and presented by students.

TEACHING METHODOLOGY

Teaching method in most our tertiary institutions is the *teacher-centered method*. In this approach, the teacher is seen as an expert who masters the subject-matter while the learners are presumed to acquire the knowledge from the instructor. It is a lecture method in which learners have little or no involvement in the teaching process and is called "closed-ended" (Ogri & Julie

C. , 2017). This method consists of seven components: developing activities used to guide the students for the lesson, teaching of new material, identifying an objective, questioning the students to get feedback from them regarding their understanding, giving feedback to the student in the needed area of improvement, and giving assignment to students. Critics point out that lecturing is mainly a one-way method of communication that does not involve significant audience participation but relies upon passive learning. However, the most important thing in lectures is “not what the lecturer says or writes but what the students have learnt and what encourages them to learn more (Olotuah, Taiwo, & Ijatuyi, 2016). The amount of knowledge assimilated by learners depends on the amount to which they are exposed and the mode/format of such indoctrination.

Various formats of lecturing in the architectural studio

Below are various formats which can be adapted to suit particular situations, disciplines and sizes of classes in lecturing.

- i. *Construction/Creative method*. The method emphasizes the practical aspect of learning. The students model forms using different materials like cardboard, wood or clay. They undertake construction drawings such as plans, sections, elevations and details. The method also tests the dexterous potentials of the students. It is particularly appropriate for design and photography and model-making courses.
- ii. *Enigmatography*: This method encourages students to think-up solutions for themselves. The students are given the opportunity to proffer solutions to problems through their sketches and designs.
- iii. *Critique sessions*: This is directly related to enigmatography. While enigmatography is employed to solve puzzling situations, the critique session helps in preventing/points out grey areas that needs to be streamlined.
- iv. *The case study method*: This method provides realistic approach towards solving problems based on existing scenarios. The goal is to make their solution a better option than the existing scenario.
- iv. *Analytic Method*: The lecturer involves the students in activities of collation, analysis and presentation of data. It comprises surveys, semi-structured interviews, questionnaire administration, and field trips (Butler, 2021).

THE ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN STUDIO

The studio is a workspace where students explore a set of skills with or without the presence of an instructor. Additionally, Ledewitz (1985) described the architectural design studio as a physical environment where students are primarily taught three aspects of design education: (a) “a new language,” (b) “a number of new skills such as visualization and representation” and (c) architectural thinking (Ledewitz, 1985). The architectural design studio culture also functions as a classroom when a school member is present, but the studio also can function in the absence of the instructor because the concept of the design studio is for students to continually work on projects in their studio. So, in all, the architectural design studio shapes and molds the character and academic personality of the architecture student (Opiyo, 2008).

At the National Diploma level, the curriculum of the National Diploma Architectural Technology programme consists of four main components: i) General Studies/Education; ii) Foundation Courses; iii) Professional Courses; iv) Supervised Industrial Work Experience

Scheme (SIWES). The General Education component include courses in - English Language and Communication, Economics, Citizenship Education and Entrepreneurship studies. The General Education component takes up between 10 - 15% of total contact hours for the programme. Foundation Courses include in Mathematics, Pure Science, Economics, Technical Drawing, Descriptive Geometry, Statistics etc. The number of hours range between 10 - 15% of the total contact hours. Professional Courses are courses which give the students theory and practical skills needed to practice the profession at the technician/technologist level. These may account for 70-80% of the total contact hours. Supervised Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) are taken during the long vacation following the end of the second semester of the first year (National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), 2020)

The curriculum of the Higher National Diploma Architectural Technology programme consists of three main components: i) General Studies/Education; ii) Foundation Courses; iii) Professional Courses. The General Education component include courses in - English Language and Communication, Economics, Citizenship Education and Entrepreneurship studies. Others may include History, Political Science, Psychology, Geography, Philosophy etc. The General Education component range between 10 - 15% of total contact hours for the programme. Foundation Courses include Mathematics, Pure Science, Computer Studies, Tendering and Estimating, Statistics etc. The number of hours range between 10 - 15% of the total contact hours. Professional Courses are courses, which give the students theory and practical skills needed to practice the profession at the technician/technologist level. These may account for 70-80% of the total contact hours (National Board for Technical Education, 2020).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The objectives of the research are to:

- investigate the coverage, direction and emphasis of the architectural design course particularly with reference to assessment in the schools selected as case studies;
- examine the pedagogical methods adopted for teaching and learning in the design studio of the schools investigated; and
- examine the methods of assessment and evaluation of the architectural design course in the selected schools.

Subjective sampling was used to select two NBTE/ARCON accredited schools of architecture from southeast Nigeria as case studies for the study. The two schools are the Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, Imo State and Abia State Polytechnic Aba, Abia State cutting across both federal and state institutions.

Primary data for the study were obtained from participant observation and semi-structured interviews conducted in the two schools. Members of staff of the departments were interviewed on the structure, organization and philosophy of the schools. The semi-structured interviews examined pedagogical issues on the study of architectural design courses. In particular, teaching methodology and learning in the design studio, and assessment and evaluation of students' creative outputs were examined in both schools. Secondary data were obtained from university publications (students' calendar, handbooks, course synopsis) obtained from both schools.

Curriculum of the Architectural Design courses at The Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, Imo State

At the National Diploma and Higher National Diploma levels, design courses are taught in two (2) academic sessions of four (4) semesters at each level. Instructors, headed by a senior academic staff, are assigned to handle the course by guiding and indoctrinating the students in the courses. Appropriate lecturing formats are employed for mentoring the students in design courses at various levels of the programme (Department of Architecture, Federal Polytechnic Nekede-Owerri, 2019).

ARC 111 (Basic Design)

This course totals 2 credit units with a total of 3 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The general objectives of the course range from knowing the basic elements of design to producing models and axonometric drawings of units.

ARC 121 (Architectural Design I)

This course totals 2 credit units with a total of 5 contact-hours per week of a total of 13 weeks. The general objectives of the course range from demonstrating problem solving in simple design to proposing simple design solutions.

ARC 211 (Architectural Design II)

This course totals 4 credit units with a total of 6 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The general objectives of the course range from analyzing human activities and circulation for a simple design to knowing how to design structures.

ARC 221 (Architectural Design Project)

This course totals 5 credit units with a total of 7 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The general objectives of the course range from expressing design abilities through simple projects, and knowing the processes and techniques required in communicating design information to others within the construction team. As an exit course, elaborate arrangements are made for critique sessions where a quorum of external assessors evaluate the students in a jury proceeding.

ARC 311 (Architectural Design & Project)

This course totals 5 credit units with a total of 7 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The general objectives of the course range from understanding the various technical and climatic data relating to the site location and conditions as they affect the design of residential buildings to designing residential buildings with consideration of function, form, cost, materials, climatic, environmental and cultural determinants.

ARC 321 (Architectural Design Project II)

This course totals 5 credit units with a total of 7 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The general objectives of the course range from knowing the various types of civic buildings to knowing how to design a simple civic building.

ARC 411 (Architectural Design Project III)

This course totals 5 credit units with a total of 8 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The general objectives of the course range from knowing the various types of industrial designs to understanding the fundamentals of producing industrial designs.

ARC 421 (Architectural Design Project & Report)

This course totals 6 credit units with a total of 10 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The general objectives of the course include understanding how to produce technical details gathered from a design brief, knowing to develop a detailed design and knowing how to produce standard report on a design project. As an exit course, elaborate arrangements are made for critique sessions where a quorum of external assessors evaluate the students in a jury proceeding.

Curriculum of Architectural Design courses at The Abia State Polytechnic, Aba, Abia State

At the Abia State Polytechnic, the same scenario basically plays out just like in The Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri. The National Diploma and Higher National Diploma levels, design courses are taught in two (2) academic sessions of four (4) semesters at each level. Allocation of design courses to instructors, however, does not follow a particular order as assignment is completely based on staff's disposition. Lecturing formats are employed according to the instructors' discretion (Abia State Polytechnic, Aba., 2020).

ARC 111 (Basic Design)

This course totals 3 credit units with a total of 3 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The course is designed to develop students' interest and creative ability in architecture.

ARC 121 (Architectural Design I)

This course totals 4 credit units with a total of 5 contact-hours per week of a total of 13 weeks. This course is designed to introduce students to architectural design through studio exercises and lectures dealing with Function, form and aesthetics.

ARC 211 (Architectural Design II)

This course totals 4 credit units with a total of 6 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. This course is designed to acquaint students with the basic tenets to produce a simple architectural design.

ARC 221 (Architectural Design Project & Report)

This course totals 6 credit units with a total of 7 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. This course is designed to provide students with knowledge and skills to design a simple project.

ARC 311 (Advanced Architectural Design I)

This course totals 5 credit units with a total of 7 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. The course is designed to create an understanding of the processes involved in architectural design activities dealing with form, function, aesthetics, structural stability, circulation, space analyses and environmental considerations.

ARC 321 (Advanced Architectural Design II)

This course totals 5 credit units with a total of 7 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. This course is intended to provide students with the understanding of the underlining factors in civic design.

ARC 411 (Advanced Architectural Design III)

This course totals 5 credit units with a total of 8 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. This course is designed to provide students with the knowledge of understanding factors to be considered in the design of agro-industrial buildings.

ARC 421 (Advanced Architectural Design Project & Report)

This course totals 7 credit units with a total of 10 contact-hours per week of a total of 15 weeks. This course is designed to provide students with knowledge and skill of the ability to present, design projects and display to the optimum.

A review of the design studio of both schools

The studio is the nexus of teaching and learning in accredited schools of architecture. To this end, the studio is targeted to improve cognitive, psychomotor and affective development of the students. In the institutions studied, the design lecturers, referred to as studio masters, have the responsibility of guiding the students through their schemes and nurture their thoughts and ideas into feasible and viable presentations. The goal is to allow each student develop at his/her own pace by creating avenue for them to exhibit their own persuasions. The bias of the studio master is relegated to the background as learning is student-centered.

In both institutions, schemes are presented as theory in briefs and expounded upon in discussion classes where students are briefed upon what is expected of them. This involves explanation on the background of each scheme, its scope and plausible objectives which must be identifiable in the final design. In the Federal Polytechnic Nekede, the studio masters also go the extra length of using audio-visual devices like projectors and laptop computers to hold expository sessions where related schemes are analyzed and expounded upon. A lot of emphasis is placed on originality of authorship, creativity, functionality and communication. Originality of authorship is sacrosanct though students are allowed to draw inspiration from sources that exude arrant dexterity and absolute imaginative prowess. Creativity comes in when such imagination is given form and functionality. At the end, the student is able to communicate to the jurors how feasible the project is. This is assessed in the locution column of the score sheet. The studio master is also expected to deploy cogitation tactics to get them thinking while adopting critique skills to get them back to coherency if they deviate from standards. While case studies are part of documentation for individual students, field trips are part of departmental arrangements where students are taken to institutions, workshops, exhibitions and material fairs to improve upon their learning experiences outside the design studio. By this, the students get firsthand experience of real-life situations. In both schools, this feature of learning is not very popular. The last fieldtrip students from The Federal Polytechnic Nekede-Owerri undertook was in 2010 while department of architecture, Abia State Polytechnic, Aba has no records of fieldtrips for its students.

The jury session is where students are assessed at the end of each semester in both schools. In such sessions, students are required to present their schemes to a quorum of jurors who assess and evaluate the students' works through a weighting system 70% (summation of jury scores)-30% (studio master's critique sessions, students' reports). A viable quorum comprises of not less than three (3) jurors. Biased scoring is mitigated by careful identification and elimination of score sheets that have digressive patterns.

Assessment patterns captured in score sheets of the two institutions indicate that case studies and design composition and functionality have substantial weightings. While case

studies are weighted an average of 18/70, design composition and functionality are weighted an average of 21.5/70. It was also observed that the student's general performance in conduct of case studies was low in both schools. In Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, students' average performance in case studies from 2015-2016 to 2018-2019 academic sessions was 38.67% and 41% at ND and HND levels (Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, 2019). Their counterparts in the Abia State Polytechnic performed lower at 32% and 39.43% at ND and HND levels within the same study time frame (Abia State Polytechnic, Aba., 2020). This trend shows that there is a gap in the conduct and documentation of case studies carried out by these students which needs to be promptly addressed.

THE PEDAGOGY OF CASE STUDIES

There is no denying the fact that case studies are very important to the training of students in schools of architecture. This is explicitly noted in pages 66 and 26 of the NBTE Curriculum and Course Specification for ND/HND Architectural Technology (National Board for Technical Education, 2020).

Case studies allows studio masters to address specific pedagogical issues and to develop higher-order skills in students. The case method can also be used in a very effective way in order to move students gradually up the cognitive skills ladder from the low skills levels of *knowledge, comprehension* and *application* to the higher and more desirable skills of *analysis, synthesis* and *evaluation* (University of Bristol, 2021). However, it is one thing to understand the importance of case studies and completely another issue to conduct a viable case study. Observation of evaluated case studies of institutions studied showed that more needs to be done in that respect from both the studio masters and the students. The buck rests on the side of the studio masters to show students how to conduct and present a viable case study. This can be done by acting as chaperones on fieldtrips, showing students what to capture, sketch and documents to collate. Thereafter, the studio masters must show the students how to organize such data into plates, figures and diagrams; properly annotated and cited.

Studio masters also need to update their skills and knowledge on how to key into the Independent Assessors Correlation Module of evaluating case studies before the students present them to jurors. This module allows the use of case studies to guide the students on how to formulate their design considerations based on scores/values assigned by external assessors. This is made possible through the input, by way of weightings, of the external assessors. These external assessors must cut across both the professional and academic genres to make for a more balanced assessment. It is the job of the studio masters to approach these resource persons for their students. All completed modules are submitted to the external assessors for assessment through the studio masters who re-distribute them back to the students for analysis and extraction after assessment.

CONCLUSION

The paper reviews the design studio of the Departments of Architecture of The Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri and Abia State University, Aba, Abia State. It asserts that the design studio is central to architectural programme, training of students and the practice of architecture. The quality of the human environment is the principal concern in architecture. Thus, architectural education strives to train professionals who would understand the nature of the human problem in its environmental context and possess the intellectual and aesthetic skills to create relevant and expressive design solutions (Olotuah, Taiwo, & Ijatuyi, 2016). This way, the learning objectives of the architecture design studio which includes producing architectural students skilled in critical, creative and pragmatic thinking becomes feasible.

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